

Kirk and Tucker “Development and application of a scoring system for septum injuries in beef calves with and without a nose flap”

Supplemental Table S3. Raw means, SE, and 95% CI, along with model outputs.

Measurement	Treatment				DF	model	P-value
	FLAP ENTIRE (n=28)		FLAP PARTIAL (n=13)				
	Means (SE)	95% CI	Means (SE)	95% CI			
Weight, kg	249 (6)	[244.6, 253.4]	242 (7)	[237.9, 246.7]	not applicable	Wilcoxon Signed Rank	0.393
Septum width, mm	39 (0.4)	[38.8, 39.2]	39 (0.6)	[38.1, 38.8]	39	Two sample T- test	0.464